

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

GAS LOOP (IT)

RENURE (BE)

SOS_AQUAE
(IT)

POCKETBOER 2
(BE)

FERTICOOP-GO
(ES)

Grass2Algae
(BE)

Manure
Management
Tool (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure
Concentrator
(ES)

Duncannon Blue
Flag Farming (IE)

Biorefinery
Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Manure Management Tools

For the Improvement of Agricultural Fertilization, Crop Quality and Environmental Protection

Analysis of manure treatment strategies with uncovered ponds to identify weak points (GHG and ammonia emissions, efficiency, costs, etc.) and to optimize it at farm or cooperative level.

Activity

Set up of an experimental device to analyse emissions from different slurry origin and different treatments (straw and acidification). The analysed gases emissions were NH₃, CH₄ and N₂O. Four ponds:

1. Control pond: fresh slurry without treatments
2. "Acid pond": fresh slurry acidified with H₂SO₄ (95-98%) 5.78 pH.
3. "Straw pond": fresh slurry covered by 2,963kg of straw
4. Digested slurry from a biogas plant

Results

- Higher temperature at the "straw pond" and lower temperatures at the "acid pond"
- "Acid pond" presents greater stability in ammonium during winter, which means less emissions.
- "Straw pond" presents greater stability in ammonium during spring-summer period.
- "Straw pond" shows greater pH stability during all year.
- "Acid pond" shows less ammonia and CH₄ emissions during all year. N₂O emissions are insignificant.

Experimental device for emissions analysis in ponds

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